

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SOCIAL MEDIA ADVERTISEMENT ON BUYING DECISION OF HOSPITALITY MANAGEMENT STUDENTS OF DLSU-D DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7731882>

Published Date: 14-March-2023

Abstract: Society lives its lives in a way that allows them to adapt to changing circumstances. The emergence of the new coronavirus, also known as Covid-19, has impacted nearly every area of people's lives by early 2020. Current and potential customers to provide a more dynamic experience and increase loyalty. The article is discussing how companies are using social media for marketing as their lifeline in surviving their business. To be more specific, the hospitality industry would be the main highlight as companies and businesses in the hospitality industry shifted and adjusted more during the pandemic. This inquiry aims to show the effectivity of media publicizing as a promoting instrument in buyer conduct for organizations in the cordiality business utilizing the EBK Model. In investigating this phenomenon in terms of the effectiveness of social media advertising in purchasing decisions during the Covid19 pandemic, researchers try to answer the following questions; demographic profile, effectiveness of advertisements on during the covid-19 pandemic through the EBK Model in the hospitality industry, is there a significant discrepancy between the respondents' demographic profile and the assessment of the effectiveness of social media ads related to the EBK model and what possible Marketing strategies on customer buying decisions can be proposed.

Keywords: Social Media Advertisement, Hospitality Management, EBK Model, Covid-19, Pandemic.

I. INTRODUCTION

Society lives its lives in a way that allows them to adapt to changing circumstances. The emergence of the new coronavirus, also known as Covid-19, has impacted nearly every area of people's lives by early 2020. As a result, it has affected almost every aspect of life including buying and purchasing. With the imposition of quarantine and safety measures among communities. The community shifted its buying processes online. The emergence of social media as a market had expanded at the start of 2020. According to Mason et al. (2020), Online media gives channels to purchasers to draw in with others without having actual touch when social distance is far and wide.

The sudden change impacted not just the buying process but also the engagement of businesses and companies to social media marketing. Forstadt (2021) article: During COVID19, social media has become the lifeblood of many corporate consumers. This allows businesses to not only continue conversations in real time, but also rethink how they connect.

Current and potential customers to provide a more dynamic experience and increase loyalty. The article is discussing how companies are using social media for marketing as their lifeline in surviving their business. To be more specific, the hospitality industry would be the main highlight as companies and businesses in the hospitality industry shifted and adjusted more during the pandemic.

In an article by Peek (2021), A lot of companies had struggled to recover from the pandemic, but the hospitality industry has been badly affected. Hospitality and tourist industries, in particular, have struggled to recover losses because of the COVID-19 pandemic, while some have been able to begin rebuilding by pivoting their business model or plan.

This inquiry aims to show the effectivity of media publicizing as a promoting instrument in buyer conduct for organizations in the cordiality business utilizing the EBK Model, featuring which step has the most grounded relationship with online media promoting and which has no relationship at all with changes in the shopper's segment factors.

Other and earlier studies focused on people's behavior, such as mental health during pandemic or pandemic prevention and health practices. However, little to no attention has been given to the consumers' behavior or also known as buying decisions. In addition, existing studies that already tackled the buying decision had focused more on different industries such as fashion, products, and services. Minimal to no studies had specifically focused on the hospitality industry.

Investigating this study will give a better understanding and can establish a relation. It is in the midst of the effectiveness of social media targeting and purchasing decisions using the SFBC model. This study holds significance not only to the market and businesses like hotels, restaurants, and the tourism industry but also to the economy of a country. According to Salesforce Survey (2019), 76% of customers expect businesses to know what they want and to understand their needs. Furthermore, in order to understand the demands and preferences of consumers, research such as that carried out in this study will serve as a starting point for assessing consumer behavior. Nevertheless especially, this study. Aims to determine the effectiveness of social media advertising on buying decision of the DLSU-D hospitality management students. As part of the community, both the researchers had also shifted their buying process online. They were curious to know if social media advertising has an effect on the buying decision of the people during the Covid-19 pandemic and specifically on the buying decision in the hospitality industry. Other factors affecting this decision will further enhance their understanding of their own and others. The result of their study can help another strand of the community not only in the society but also in the economy.

A. Background of the Study

Consumer behavior is an essential part of the market dynamics. They are a key component to determine what influences the buying decision. As stated by Marjanen et al. (2019), generational cohort membership shares similar values which affect attitudes, preferences, as well as shopping habits and behaviour. During covid-19 consumers' priority and reference may have changed and critical situations impel human behavior to different paths with some aspect of behavior being unalterable. In accordance with Mehta et al. (2020), This shows that with economic instability due to covid-19, consumers do experience change in behavior is questionable.

Market came to thought about new things, find about things they might need or is a need , and the more they think about items, the more decisions they have. Nobody needs to settle on awful buy choices, so what online media gives is keen numerous decisions as opposed to poor or only numerous decisions. According to Pantano (2020) point out that consumers have reviewed their shopping habits and at the same time have discovered benefits from services they had never used before. For instance, some consumers are switching to online purchases, discovering the safety and benefits of home deliveries, store pick-up, and cashless payment.

The result of the study, titled "the role of social media advertisements on the consumers ibuying behavior", resulted that 94% of the marketers use sms media as a way to advertise their products. The study further concluded and describe the relationship of social media advertising to the consumer's behavior as in between moderate to strong. The study is mainly focusing on the significance of social media advertising, but still, the conclusion of the study showed a relevant relationship between the two variables.

In an article by ClooTrack PH (2021), "Consumers who are influenced by social media are 4 times more likely to spend more on purchases". The statement further states that 29% of consumers are more likely to shop on social media on the same day because of their influence. In the article's conclusion, it was stated that the social media has, content, promotion, advertising, and visuals are capable to influence the buying decision of the consumers. It also has an effect on the brands' reputation and influencers. But furthermore, it will be about the social activeness of businesses or online businesses.

The study of Arceo et al. (2020) titled "The impact of social media advertising in intention to purchase in the restaurant industry", resulted that online social media advertisement has impacted the purchase intentions of the respondents. The study further claimed that due to the frequency of social media use the consumers engage more in purchasing. In addition, the said industry is essential to the consumers which added to the factor of effectivity.

B. Scope and Delimitation

The scope of the study will limit its purpose on the effectiveness of social media advertising specifically on Social Media-Plattformen wie Facebook, Youtube, Twitter, Pinterest, Reddit, Instagram and its effect on buying decision of Hospitality Management Students. Furthermore, the said buying will focus on the companies offered by the hospitality industry products.

This study delimits its purpose to only establish the effect and be able to explain the relationship between variables, any other topic besides social media advertising, buying decision and covid-19 pandemic will not be included in the study.

C. Conceptual Framework

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework

D. Statement of the Problem

In investigating this phenomenon in terms of the effectiveness of social media advertising in purchasing decisions during the Covid19 pandemic, researchers try to answer the following questions:

1. What is a demographic profile?
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Gender
 - 1.3 Allowance
 - 1.4 Social Media Time
2. How do the respondents assess the effectiveness of advertisements on during the covid-19 pandemic through the EBK Model in the hospitality industry?
 - Need Recognition
 - Information Search
 - Evaluation of alternativeness
 - The Buying Decision
 - Post-Purchase Evaluation
3. Is there a significant discrepancy between the respondents' demographic profile and the assessment of the effectiveness of social media ads related to the EBK model?
4. Based on the study, what possible Marketing strategies on customer buying decisions can be proposed.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

This research uses a quantitative, descriptive study tool to illustrate the current effectiveness of social media advertising for purchasing decisions during the Covid 19 pandemic. According to McCombes (2019), Descriptive studies aim to explain population, situation, or phenomenon accurately and systematically. The nominated population will be students of BS Hospitality Management at the University of Delasal Dasmariñas. The SFBC model should be used to determine a systematic reference to social media advertising for purchasing decision trends for the current situation of the Covid 19 pandemic. Online surveys are used to collect data.

B. Locale of the Study

The study is conducted at DLSU-D This study locale was chosen as the researchers are currently studying at the said university of, specifically to the department of Science in Hospitality Management. The outcome of the research was not the only benefit the students, but also the administration of the said department and also the community in the hospitality industry.

C. Population and Sampling Technique

The sample of the are the students of Hospitality Management of the De La Salle University- Dasmariñas. According to Brenner and Duggan (2012), College students engage more on social media by 69% higher than high school students and working adults. Hospitality Management was chosen as they can give better perception and insight to the hospitality industry compared to other departments in the college. According to Lashley (2017), Students who are already studying and developing in a certain field can give a better impression of a specific industry or field.

Stratified Sampling are used to determine study respondents. According to Murphy (2021), it is used to ensure that each subgroup in the population is properly sampled. As a result, stratified random samples provide better population coverage because researchers have more control over subgroups and everyone is included in the sample. The researchers will have more control over the population assessment if they use this sampling technique. Because the population is so huge, the researchers can speed up the data gathering and analysis by utilizing stratified sampling to choose the appropriate samples.

D. Data Gathering Procedure

The data gathering procedure reflects how the collected data was obtained, interpreted, and analyzed. According to Barrot (2017), the measure followed is divided into three phases: before, after, and after data collection. In order to provide a structured data collection process, researchers must have a questionnaire and prepare to perform an online survey in their corresponding target respondents.

According to Witz, Self-made questionnaires are made up of self-administered questionnaire that consists open and closed question. With this type of method, the researchers can generate more specific questions and understandable ones that can help utilize the collection of data more smoothly. The Questionnaire will be checked and validated by a statistician to test the reliability of its content. After the validation, it will be distributed to the target respondents.

E. Research Instrument

The researchers used an online survey form, an online survey, according to Usability, is a systematic questionnaire that your target audience fills out via the internet, usually by filling out a form. Because the epidemic makes it difficult for researchers to collect data in person, an online survey will be used, with social media communication serving as a means of connecting with responders. It is composed of a Likert scale and multiple-choice to collect the needed data from the respondents. This chosen instrument is used in the gathering of data to test the validity and reliability of the research study being conducted. It composes of 30 modified questions derived from the SOP of this research. It was validated by the statistician before disseminating the form to the respondents.

F. Statistical Treatment of Data

This section of the study discusses the statistical method to be used to measure the data provided by the respondents. Different statistical methods were utilized in order to determine if there is a relationship between the variables. Below are the selected statistical tool methods to be used to accomplish the purpose of the study.

Descriptive statistics helps to understand and elaborate a specific given data through summarizing the samples and measures of the data. As studied by Kenton (2019), descriptive statistics are divided into central tendency measurements and variability measurements. It is used to determine the mode of the data. This implies a simple quantitative summary of a data

set that has been collected. It allows researchers to understand the experiment or data collection in-depth and informs researchers what they need to bring the data into perspective. In relation to this study, using descriptive statistics the variables, social media advertising, and buying decisions during a pandemic, will be elaborated and be examined with simple graphics analysis.

The Pearson R method is used to determine if a relationship is present between two or more variables. Pearson's R is defined in statistics as the measurement of the strength of the relationship between two variables and their association with each other. Since the study is trying to prove the effectiveness of social media advertising to the buying decision. This tool will also present statistical data that can provide evidence for the result and can be the basis for the output.

This method served as a medium to provide numerical findings and to describe the result. After the collection of the data from the respondents, researchers created a database that contains the raw scores of each respondent.

Slovin's system is used to decide the ideal pattern length from the population. This enables the survey decide the exact pattern length of the survey.

Slovin's formula is used to calculate the sample size necessary to achieve a certain confidence interval when sampling a population. Lastly, the Leximancer Application will be used to automatically analyze the data. It is a computerized system that can help this study to produce a sentiment analysis without bias in the data. Leximancer is computer software that conducts quantitative content analysis using a machine learning technique. It learns what the main concepts are in a text and how they relate to each other. It conducts a thematic analysis and a relational (or semantic) analysis of the interview data.

III. CONCLUSION

Demographic Profile

As for the age, the results of the research show that the majority of the respondents belong to the age bracket of 20–21 years old with a frequency of 71 and percentage of 41.5%. This exhibits that people between the ages of 20-21 tends to spend most of their time during pandemic on social media buying needs and wants. For the year level, the results of the research show that the majority of the respondents are 4th year college with a frequency of 56 and percentage of 32.7%. This exhibits that 4th year college students tend to spend most of their time during pandemic on social media buying needs and wants. In weekly allowance, the results of the research show that the majority of the respondents has a weekly allowance of less than ₱1000 with a frequency of 115 and percentage of 67.3%. This exhibits that the allowance of less than ₱1000 that the students can only use for buying needs and wants in social media. During the time spent in social media, the results of the research shows that the majority of the respondents spent 5-7 hours in social media during pandemic with a frequency of 56 and percentage of 32.7%. This exhibits that during pandemic the respondents spent most their time browsing in social media.

Factors affecting the effectiveness of social media advertisements on the buying decision during covid-19 pandemic through the EBK Model in hospitality industry

For the need recognition, research shows that majority of the respondents are agree it the overall perceived effect of Need Recognition with the overall mean of 3.322. Majority of the respondents agreed on recognition and advertisements of the products the customer wants and needs. Information search, research shows that majority of the respondents are agree it the overall perceived effect of Information Search with the overall mean of 3.092. Majority of the respondents agreed on relying on the advertisement and reviews before purchasing products in online shopping in social media. In Evaluation of Alternativeness, research shows that majority of the respondents are agree it the overall perceived effect of Evaluation of Alternativeness with the overall mean of 2.804. Majority of the respondents agreed on purchasing products that is known brand and advertised in social media platforms. The Buying Decision, research shows that majority of the respondents are agree it the overall perceived effect of The Buying Decision with the overall mean of 2.864. Majority of the respondents agreed on spending money only on the products that was advertised in social media flatforms. Furthermore, Post-Purchase Behavior research shows that majority of the respondents are agree it the overall perceived effect of Post-Purchase Behavior with the overall mean of 3.041. Majority of the respondents agreed on purchasing more in social media because of the satisfaction after receiving the product.

IV. RECOMMENDATION

Several research on consumer behavior toward internet purchasing, as well as demographic profile that impacts on such behavior, have been undertaken in recent years. According to research findings, DLSU-D students are more familiar with internet shopping, they find it more convenient, and they have greater intention to shop online since the Covid-19 Pandemic

began, and even when the lockdown is lifted, students tend to buy things on social media. Students tend to purchase from trusted and well-known brands with high quality products.

Researchers also recommend double-checking the reviews and asking someone who has already purchased the product if they recommend it, or asking the seller directly for a better understanding of the product. Since scamming is also part of online business and some of its modus operandi take advantage of people who have less knowledge about online shopping, trust in online shopping and the name of the business are being ruined, and conflicts are beginning to rise.

Future researchers can utilize this study for better reference and understanding of the same topic of The Effectiveness of Social Media on Buying Decisions During the COVID-19 Pandemic that will be conducted by future researchers. Future researchers can learn more about online purchasing with the help of social media during the COVID-19 pandemic and help society study and understand people that prefer purchasing on social media platforms.

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